

ANALYSIS OF FREE VIBRATION OF A PEDESTRIAN GRP BRIDGE WITH SKEW CABLE STAYS

Gong Zhiyu, Feng Guangzhan, Wang Qingyuan
(Chengdu University of Science and Technology, China)

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this paper is to present the work in analyzing free vibration and computing free vibration frequencies of the pedestrian GRP bridge with skew cable stays built in Chongqing Jiaotong Institute with analytical method and energy method. By both methods, the results are in a good approximation and have also been verified by field tests on the GRP bridge.

The main frame of the bridge is a box structure made of GRP boneycomb sandwich plates. The local free vibration frequencies of top plates and longitudinal webs of the box structure have also been calculated and the results are satisfactory.

1. Free vibration frequency of the main beam of a GRP bridge

(1) Considering the main beam as an elastic foundation beam

Fig. 1

Reducing the tractive force of cable stays to vertical reactive force of distributed supports of the GRP bridge, which we consider to be an elastic foundation beam (Fig.1) with an elastic coefficient being

$$C=C = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n K_i}{l} \quad \text{where} \quad K_i = \frac{E A_s s_i}{L_i} \sin^2 \alpha_i \quad (1)$$

Then the differential equation of the main beam in vibration becomes

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 y}{\partial x^4} = -\bar{m} \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} - C^2 y \quad (2)$$

Resolving equation (2) and basing on constraint condition of the beam with joint supports on two ends, we find free vibration frequency of the main beam as below

$$\omega_1^2 = \frac{k^4 EI + C}{\bar{m}} = \frac{\alpha^2 \pi^4}{l^4} (j^4 + \beta) \quad (j=1,2,\dots) \quad \text{where } \alpha^2 = \frac{EI}{\bar{m}}, \quad \beta = \frac{Cl^4}{EI\pi^4} \quad (3)$$

(2) Calculation of free vibration frequency with energy method Based on the law of energy conservation, we have

$$W_{\max} = V_{\max} \quad (4)$$

Referring to Fig.2, we could find the maximum kinetic energy of the whole bridge system, i.e.

$$W_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 \left[\int_0^l \bar{m} y^2(x) dx + \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{m}_s \frac{y_i^2}{L_i^2} \int_0^{L_i} s^2 ds \right] \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2

The potential energy of system consists of three parts, besides potential energy of main beam and cables, the work done by the secondary deformation of cables during periodic vibration must be considered, thus the total maximum potential energy is

$$V_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_0^l EI \left(\frac{d^2 y(x)}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^2 \sin^2 \alpha_i}{L_i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^3 \sin \alpha_i \cos^2 \alpha_i}{L_i^2} \right] \quad (6)$$

Putting equation (5) and (6) into equation (4), we get

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\int_0^l EI \left(\frac{d^2 y(x)}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^2 \sin^2 \alpha_i}{L_i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^3 \sin \alpha_i \cos^2 \alpha_i}{L_i^2}}{\int_0^l \bar{m} y^2(x) dx + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{m}_s y_i^2 L_i} \quad (7)$$

(3) Basic vibration frequency of calculation in comparison with test value Fig.3 shows the cross section of the main beam, depending on dimensions and densities of main beam and cables and applying equations (3) and (7), we obtain basic vibration frequencies $f = \omega/2\pi = 3.26\text{Hz}$ and $f = 3.3\text{Hz}$ respectively. Both values are approximate to the value $f = 3.15\text{Hz}$ of field test which is measured from the bridge in vibration with strain gauges. The comparison demonstrates that the reduced beam could bear a satisfactory basic vibration frequency.

Fig. 3

2. Free vibration of surface plates and longitudinal webs of the box beam of GRP bridge

The main beam of GRP bridge is a box structure which consists of surface plate and transverse and longitudinal webs being made of sandwich honeycomb plates (Fig.3). We analyze free vibration frequency of a surface plate confined by two transverse webs

and two longitudinal webs to be abstracted as a simple support rectangular plate (Fig.4) with an analytical method and a formula is derived as blow

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{m} \left\{ D \left[\left(\frac{m}{a} \right)^4 + \left(\frac{n}{b} \right)^4 \right] + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \left(\frac{mn}{ab} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4

which gives the basic vibration frequency $f = 67\text{Hz}$.

A longitudinal web is reduced to a rectangular plate with boundary condition shown as Fig.5, of which a formula to account free vibration frequency is derived with Reyleigh's method, it is

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{m} \left\{ D \left[\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{a} \right)^4 + \frac{41}{64} \left(\frac{1}{b} \right)^4 \right] - \frac{5D_{12}}{8a^2b^2} + \frac{5D_{66}}{4a^2b^2} \right\} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 5

From the above equation we have got basic free vibration frequency $f=904\text{H}$ for middle longitudinal web and $f=600\text{H}$ for two side longitudinal webs, because the latters have less thickness than the former.

The results show that the local parts are in a better vibration condition than the whole bridge system. By the way, we have also done a stability check about the GRP bridge in another sister paper.